

Evaluation of Postnatal Care Services Utilization in an Urban Area of Haryana: Stakeholder Perspectives and Recommendations**Bhumika Bhatt¹, Neelam², Awadhesh Kumar³, Aarti Sharma⁴, Devendra Kumar⁵, J.S. Malik⁶**^{1,5}Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, ASMC Firozabad, Uttar Pradesh²Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Madhav Prasad Tripathi Medical College & Hospital, Siddharthnagar, Uttar Pradesh³Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, ASMC, Ayodhya, Uttar Pradesh⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Community Medicine, Madhubani Medical College & Hospital, Madhubani, Bihar⁶Ex. Professor, Department of Community Medicine, PGIMS, Rohtak, Haryana

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Abstract:**Background:** Labor, birth and immediate postnatal care are the most critical period for newborn and maternal survival. Unfortunately, the majority of mothers and newborns in low- and middle-income countries do not receive optimal care during these periods. Postnatal period being the first six weeks after birth is critical to the health and survival of a mother and her newborn.**Material & Methods:** A cross-sectional study was carried out among all women who delivered during the study period. Deliveries were traced telephonically and with the help of Anganwadi worker and health workers and were interviewed using pre-designed pretested interview schedule. Categorical data was analysed using Chi square test. Data analysis was performed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20.0 software.**Results:** Majority (90.4%) deliveries were vaginal. Most of the deliveries (91.3%) were institutional deliveries and majority (62.0%) of them were conducted in a government institute. Majority 98.6% of new borns cried after birth. Skin to skin contact during delivery was practiced in only 34.6% of cases. Majority of new-borns, 95.7% were dried and wrapped immediately after birth. More than ninety percent babies (95.4%) were massaged and kajal was applied on eyes of 92.5% of babies.**Conclusion:** In the end the study concludes that though some practices like percentage of institutional deliveries, drying of baby after birth, colostrums feeding, bedding in were good but still some practices like early initiation of breast feeding, birth vaccination, pre-lacteal feeding needs improvement.**Keywords:** Evaluation, Postnatal Care, Haryana.

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Introduction

Labor, birth and the immediate postnatal period are the most critical for newborn and maternal survival. Unfortunately, the majority of mothers and newborns in low- and middle-income countries do not receive optimal care during these periods. The postnatal period being defined as the first six weeks after birth; is critical to the health and survival of a mother and her newborn.

The most vulnerable time for both is during the hours and days after birth. Lack of care in this time period may result in death or disability as well as missed opportunities to promote healthy behaviors, affecting women, newborns, and children. Urban India has 28% of the national population and is predicted to increase to 33% by 2026 though on

average health indicators, the situation in cities is better than in rural areas, the enormous social and economic stratification with in urban areas results in significant health inequalities. [1, 2] Care practices immediately after birth play an important role in reducing maternal mortality and morbidity. All new born get care according to the perceptions of and socio-cultural behaviour of the society.

New born care is strongly influenced by the women's social status, health status and home care practices for newborn. In developing countries nearly half of all mothers and newborns do not receive skilled care during and immediately after birth. Up to two thirds of newborn deaths can be prevented if known, effective health measures are

provided at birth and during the first week of life. While home births are very common in developing countries, only 13% of women in these countries receive postnatal care in the first 24 hours. [3] Community-based trials from Maharashtra and Uttar Pradesh in India showed 62% and 54% reductions in neonatal mortality, respectively, through multiple prenatal and postnatal home visits by trained community level health workers.[3,4]

Home Based Post Natal Care (HBPNC) programme in India was started in 2009 as Norway India Partnership Initiative (NIPI), provider includes Anganwadi Worker (AWW), Auxiliary Nurse Midwife (ANM) and the Medical Officers.[5] According to WHO if birth is in a health facility, mothers and newborns should receive postnatal care in the facility for at least 24 hours after birth. If birth is at home, the first postnatal contact should be as early as possible within 24 hours of birth. At least three additional postnatal contacts are recommended for all mothers and newborns, on day 3 (48–72 hours) and between days 7–14 after birth, and six weeks after birth. Newborn mortality is one of the world's most neglected health problems. Every year nearly 40% of all under-five child deaths are among newborn infants, babies in their first 28 days of life or the neonatal period. Three quarters of all newborn deaths occur in the first week of life and 25% to 45% occur within the first 24 hours. [6,7]

In India, where a quarter of neonatal deaths of world occur, around 50-60% of all infant deaths occur within first month of life and 1.3 million of children die within 1st 4 weeks of life (4) and more than half die within a year as per NFHS3. Current neonatal mortality rate of India is 29 per 1000 live births. [8] The main causes of newborn deaths are prematurity and low-birth weight, infections, asphyxia (lack of oxygen at birth) and birth trauma. These causes account for nearly 80% of deaths in this age group.[9]

In the end any effort to improve the survival of mothers and children requires intervention at various stages of life including the adolescence phase, pre-pregnancy period, during pregnancy and delivery, after childbirth and then in the newborn period and childhood. Therefore a lifecycle approach has been adopted under NRHM and is referred to as RMNCH+A approach. RMNCH+A stands for Reproductive, Maternal, Newborn, Child and Adolescent health. With this background, this study was conducted to assess utilization of postnatal services provided in urban area of Rohtak, Haryana and to study the socio-cultural practices in postnatal period.

Materials and Methods

A community based, descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted in an urban area of Rohtak to

the postnatal care of pregnant women and the socio-cultural factors having a bearing on the same. All pregnant women who delivered during the study period were included in the study. The population of the area as on March 31st 2012 was 23997 (at the time of plan) and considering the birth rate of 17.2 per thousand population, 412 live births were expected during the study period. Therefore the minimum sample size of 412 pregnant women was proposed for the study.

A list of all pregnant women, who delivered, during the study period was made with the help of ANC registers available at the Urban Health Centers and with the help of Anganwadi workers. Those who agreed to participate were included in the study and an informed consent was taken. Deliveries were traced with the help of health workers, AWWs or telephonically. The families were visited within 43-45 days of child birth and the mother or caretaker was interviewed using a predesigned and pretested semi-structured interview schedule. Data was coded and entered in SPSS Version -20 (Statistical Package for Social Studies) software. Appropriate statistical tests were applied wherever applicable.

Results

Total 443 women delivered during the study period. Out of them 12 women were not available at the time of study after three visits, 5 got aborted. Total 426 mothers were interviewed using pre-tested semi structured questionnaire by house to house to visit. Out of the total 426 deliveries 8 were still births and three neonates died so 415 mothers were interviewed regarding new-born care practices.

Majority (96%) of study subjects were Hindu by religion, Sikh (2.6%) and Muslims (1.4%). Majority (54.9%) had 6-9 members in their household followed by 1-5 members (34.7%). Nearly two-fifth (40.4%) of study participants had a monthly family income of 10,000-20,000. 90.8% of study subjects were literate. Out of them 25.1% were educated upto senior secondary, 14.6% upto matric level and only 9.2 % were illiterate. Out of 426 subjects, 83.8 % were housewives while 16.2% were working women. Mean age of mother at the time of first pregnancy was 22.6 + 2.38 years. Less than half 44.1% of study subjects had parity two followed by 35.7% who had parity one and only 0.5% belonged to para five. Only 7.3% faced abortions during previous pregnancies.

Majority (90.4%) deliveries were vaginal. Most of the deliveries (91.3%) were institutional deliveries and majority (62.0%) of them were conducted in a government institute. Most of the (95.5%) new born were term babies and only 3.8 and 0.7% were per-term and post term respectively. More than fifty percent (55.9%) of new-borns were male and

44.1% were females. Majority (87.7%) of mothers were discharged before 24 hours out of which 57.9% were discharged less than 12 hours. Around 82.7% of total deliveries were conducted by doctors followed by Staff Nurses /ANM (8.7 %), trained dais (5.4%), untrained dais (2.1%) and 1.1% by relatives. Majority 98.6% of new born cried after birth. Skin to skin contact during delivery was practiced in only 34.6% of cases. Majority 88.4% of new born were placed beside mother. Majority of new-born, 95.7% were dried and wrapped immediately after birth. More than ninety percent babies (95.4%) were massaged and kajal was applied on eyes of 92.5% of babies. Around 88.0% of new born were shifted to mother's side within one hour. Only 1.4% of them were shifted to mother after 24 hrs.

Majority (77.1%) of new born were bathed within 24 hours of birth out of which 41% were bathed 6-

12 hours of delivery. Only 22.9% were bathed after 24 hours out of which only 12.5 % were bathed on or after second day. Majority 75.9% of new borns were given prelacteal feeding. Colostrum feeding was high as 88.9% of new born were given colostrum. In 94.2% of new born breast feed was initiated within 24 hour of birth out of which, in 66.0 % it was started within two hour. Only 5.8% of new born were breast fed after 24 hours.

Overall 9.2% mothers faced problem during lactation out of which lower amount of milk was the most important problem (39.5%) followed by painful breast (34.2%). Around 40% of mothers had applied some substance on cord. Oil or ghee was the most common applicant followed by povidone iodine 21.1, cream 16.3%, turmeric powder (6.6%) and powder (4.8%).

Table 1: Vaccination status after birth

Total child vaccinated at birth	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	297	71.6
No	118	28.4
Vaccines Given		
BCG	297	71.6
OPV0	297	71.6
Hepatitis B0	196	47.2
Given free of cost		
Yes	324	78.1
No	91	21.9

Table 2: Breast feeding practices

	New born	Percentage (%)
Given Pre-lacteal feed		
Yes	315	75.9
No	100	24.1
Given Colostrum		
Yes	369	88.9
No	46	11.1
Initiation of first feed after birth		
0-2 hours	274	66.0
2-24 hours	117	28.2
24-48 hours	21	5.1
≥ 48 hours	3	0.7
Frequency of breast feeding		
≥ 8 times/day	358	86.3
< 8times/day	51	12.3
No secretion of milk	6	1.4
Problem during breast feeding		
Yes	38	9.2
No	377	90.8
Given other than breast milk		
Yes	175	42.2
No	240	57.8
Total	415	100

Discussion

In a study done by Puri S et al in Chandigarh 93.8% of babies were dried and wrapped soon after birth, 55.6% were massaged and in 28.3% kajal was applied to eyes.[10] Nimbalkar et al in their study in Gujarat found that 85.7% of babies were dried immediately after birth, kajal was applied in eyes of 35.7% babies and 97.4% of mothers and babies were placed together.[11] Nearly all (98.7%) babies were massaged and kajal was applied in the eyes of new born in a study by Kumar et al in coastal areas of South India similar to results of our study. [12]

Majority (77.1%) of babies were bathed within 24 hour of birth out of which 41% were bathed after 6-12 hours of delivery. Thakur et al in their study in urban slums of Ganda community found that all (100%) of babies were bathed within 24 hours of birth.[13] Majority 76% and 77.1% of new borns were bathed within 24 hours in studies done by Sartaj et al in urban slums of Meerut and Gupta et al in Lucknow respectively comparable to our findings.[14, 15]

In our study family type, literacy status of mothers and place of delivery were significantly associated with duration between birth and first bath. Kaphle et al in their study in Nepal also demonstrated significant association of literacy status, caste, parity of mother and place of delivery with delayed bathing comparable to our results. In accordance with our findings Chaudhary J et al in their study in rural area of Nepal also found significant association between place of delivery and delayed bathing. [16,17]

In a study by Thakur et al more than half (61.87 %) of mothers initiated the breastfeed within 2 hrs after birth comparable to our results.[13] Majority (82.50%) of mothers had given colostrum to their newborn as a first feed as a perception that colostrum might prevent the child from illness and child become healthy. Puri et al in their study in Chandigarh found that though only 38.1% of babies were initiated on breast feeding within two hour but only 5.3% were given breast milk after 24 hours which was comparable to our results.[10] Jani et al found early initiation of breast feeding was 65.5% in accordance with our study but pre-lacteal feeding was seen in only 37.7% with jaggery water as the predominant feed.[18] High pre lacteal feeding was also reported by Khan et al (80.0%) in Aligarh, Khunt et al (84%) in Ahmedabad district.[19,20] Parity and education of mother were found to have statistically significant association with initiation breast feeding. Kaphle et al also obtained significant association of maternal education and parity with early initiation of breast feeding. [16] Grover et al also found that early initiation of breast feeding was more common in primiparae and mothers and who had more than eight years of education. [21]

Less than three fourth (71.6%) of child were vaccinated at birth. All of them were given BCG and zero dose of OPV but only 47.2% of them were given zero dose of Hepatitis B. More than three fourth (78.1%) of the family members knew that vaccination is given free of cost by government. High BCG (90.4%), OPV (89.2%) and Hepatitis B (71.4%) coverage was reported by Puri et al in their study in Chandigarh.[10] In a study by Rahi et al in urban resettlement colonies of Delhi 47.5 % of babies had received BCG and OPV zero dose, 43.9% had received Hepatitis B zero dose. [22] In our study percentage of institutional deliveries was high so immunisation coverage was good as compared to Rahi et al. Low coverage of BCG and OPV zero dose in our study might be due to the reason that some private institutions are not vaccinating babies at the time of birth.

Majority (95.8%) of mothers and newborns had hospital stay of less than 48 hours out of which majority were discharged in less than 12hours. This is in contrast to data obtained by DLHS 4 which states that 34% of mothers had minimum 48 hours of stay in Rohtak.[23] Sinha et al in their study obtained similar results with majority of females had duration of stay less than 48 hours. [24]

In our study only 35.4% of study population were given home visits in post natal period. Majority 64.9% were given single post natal visit. None of the mothers and new borns was given more than 3 visits. Nothing specific information was provided in those mothers.

In a study by Sinha et al in the rural area of Mewat found that only 33.0% mothers were given first visit within 24 hours of home delivery and only 15% mothers received seven post natal visits. Despite being an urban area the coverage of post natal services was poor than rural area as in our study none of the mother received minimum three post natal visits. [24]

Post natal care utilisation was inadequate as only one third of mothers had received post natal visits. So there is need of collaborative efforts by family, community and health workers to improve the maternal and new born practices.

Conclusion

In the end the study concludes that though some practices like percentage of institutional deliveries, drying of baby after birth, colostrums feeding, bedding in were good but still some practices likes early initiation of breast feeding, birth vaccination, pre-lacteal feeding needs improvement. It can be done through awareness generation and with support of health workers and community as well as strengthening of health facilities.

Recommendations:

- Enhance female education through Education for All and incorporate primary health information in the curricula of health personnel.
- To improve postnatal care there is need to sensitise health care workers about the importance of post natal care and also train them about the elements of PNC.
- Mothers should be addressed on antenatal check-up days, in immunization clinics, newborn care, mothers group meeting in Anganwadi and during the home visits by health workers
- Prevailing unhealthy practices in the area also should be discussed with health care providers including dais and local practitioners, so that they take special action in preventing these.

Limitations:

- The present study is based on reported newborn care and not on actual observations. As a result response for some of the practices could not be obtained in case of institutional deliveries, as mothers were not aware of those.
- The survey is likely to have missed information on neonates who died before the visit of the investigator as well as mothers who were not present at the time of study.
- As well as it is also likely that due to the long and sequential nature of the study questionnaire, the interviewers' might have unknowingly influenced a change in the study parameters (knowledge, attitude and practices), which is another limitation of the study.
- Since this study was done in an urban area, the study cannot be representative of the whole state.

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